

Features mentality and methods of education

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Abstract. The article compares the Eastern and Western styles of education. The main features of these styles of education, the positions of Eastern and Western education and the behavior of the subjects of the educational process in various situations in the thesis version are determined. It is pointed out the contrast between the approaches of Eastern and Western methods of education and the need to take into account age characteristics and educational tasks that are characteristic of each age period, certain age.

Keywords: education, anxiety, development abilities, motivation.

A child's mental development depends on a large number of factors [7]. Among them are the behavioral reactions of the surrounding people and environmental factors. The child is open to new knowledge. A whole range of sensations immediately fall on a newborn baby: it feels the warmth of its mother, tastes the taste of milk, is greeted by the light of day, sees the bright spots of toys, hears a huge number of unfamiliar sounds, smells. On the question of availability intelligence

in newborns scientists until answer ambiguously, mainly pointing to the reflexive nature of children's reactions. But still, they are richer feeling child, that hers will be higher intelligence.

You can teach something to a person who is physically and mentally ready to learn at that moment. The child has the ability of the nervous system to form conditioned reflexes and memory.

In children's education, as in the future, the task, first of all, of relatives, as well as educators, teachers is to create optimal conditions for learning and development of the child's abilities, so as not to harm his mental and physical health.

When raising and developing a child from birth, it is important to take into account the peculiarities and tasks of each specific age. If you work with the baby, relying only on the personal ambitions and expectations of the parents, on their desire for the child to be first and successful in everything, it can lead to neuroses and more serious problems.

Of course, mom and dad will be happy if their child learns English, swims in the pool, learns music, and plays an instrument, but for the child himself, this carousel of activities can be very stressful. Researchers have repeatedly noted the negative impact of stress in scientific publications [1, 5, 6, 8, 9, 16, 17].

In each period of development, a child has a certain level of functional capabilities of the body, the level of functional reserves, vital energy. Naturally, under the action of excessive factors, energy resources are mobilized, but the body is already working with tension. With further growth of the action or increase in the action of excessive factors, there is a violation of adaptation, which precedes the disease. The level of adaptation capabilities is an individual value at different ages for different children. Therefore, it is easy to cross the individual limit, beyond which the adaptation capabilities will begin to strain. In the circle of various activities planned for the child, more energy is often spent than is permissible. And even at the same time, the forces are not spent in the direction in which it is necessary and due to the age-specific features of mental, physical and psychomotor development. It is

definitely negative when the physiological needs of the body, characteristic of each age period, are not met. A 5-year-old child has certain high needs for movement, motor activity, she must run, jump, play mobile games, sculpt balls in the sandbox to ensure a physiological level of motor activity. If, instead, the child is put on a chair for a long time and given a book, and then piano lessons, where you have to sit again, this is not good. There is a very high risk, or even a 100% probability, that we will receive a well-read musical child with unsatisfactory adaptation capabilities, great hidden stress, reduced functional capabilities of the cardiorespiratory system [10-15] and possibly problems with the digestive system and musculoskeletal system. Stress is especially dangerous in critical periods.

Critical periods are the stages of the most abrupt jump-like anatomical and physiological transformations, fish-like moments of development of the whole organism, its individual organs and tissues, critical stages of development, when the organism moves from one qualitative state to another. A lot of energy and strength goes into these transformations. And it is wrong to redistribute them in the direction of early intellectual development, because such a contradiction to the physiological laws that have been developed by evolution is inevitably accompanied by a low level of health and even the occurrence of a pathological reaction. At a certain point in the body, there is the weakest link, which will react when overloaded. And supporters of psychosomatics point to the problem of the growing number of allergies in children, especially in the form of such a form as bronchial asthma. They explain it so that asthma is nothing but a manifestation of the child's inability to resist the will of the parents, to say "no" to them, I don't want to do this. This is a difficult exhalation, because the pronunciation "no" is pronounced sharply on the exhale. "No" seems to be "stuck" in the respiratory tract. So, paralyzed will, difficult breathing, bronchial asthma - psychosomatics.

In today's world, China is currently experiencing an economic and intellectual rise and claims the title of a superpower. And this is thanks to the potential of its residents (high work capacity, patience, ability to learn). There is an opinion that the reason lies in the system of raising children in this eastern state, unlike in the West.

When comparing Eastern and Western methods of education, we will determine the following main points. According to the position on raising a child in the West, each child is talented in its own way. It is only necessary to help her develop, but in no case do not pressure, do not point out and do not punish for bad grades. The classic position of Chinese educators (mothers and fathers as well) is that 95% of people are lazy. Only 5% are able to organize themselves and achieve something without prompting. Others need "wonderful pendulums". Especially for children who do not yet understand that hard work and perseverance are the basis of success. Chinese parents may require their children to get only excellent grades. Moreover, in all subjects - I excel in mathematics, as well as in literature and drawing. If a Chinese child gets a good, not an excellent grade (and that never happens) - first there will be an explosion, with screams and noise. Then the unhappy Chinese mother will find a dozen or better a hundred test tasks on this subject and will do them with her child until she feels that he will definitely get an A.

Western parents can only ask their children to study better. And, if the request turns out to be unsuccessful, to shrug their shoulders, they say, he is talented in something else... And later, the same parents try to convince themselves that they are not disappointed by what successes their children have achieved

From the standpoint of the West, a child is a person from birth. He is the best, even in spite of his failures. It is necessary to nurture and respect his sense of self-worth in any situation.

The position of the East: a child is not a person until he proves his right to concessions and decisions. Adherents of Eastern education believe that Western parents are too concerned about their children's sense of self-worth. Western parents try to convince their child that they are better, regardless of grades or poor concert performances. Eastern parents believe that in this case, one of the worst things that parents can do for their child's self-esteem is to allow the child to relax and give up under the pretext: "Well, this is who I am...". Chinese parents value strength, not weakness . And they teach their children the same.

From the West's point of view: the child should decide for himself what to do. A child owes nothing to his parents. The main thing is for her to be happy. In the East, it is believed that a child is raw clay, from which a "work of art" - an adult successful person - can be molded only through painstaking training and strict upbringing. Therefore, in the East, only parents decide what children will learn and what they will learn. The child's sense of happiness is not taken into account.

It's hard to enjoy what you're not good at. Therefore, children do not like to play scales; do not like to do painful stretching during training; do not like to learn the multiplication table and solve complex problems. They don't succeed (as it always happens with beginners) - that's why the first reaction is: "I don't get pleasure, I'm not happy, I don't want to do it!". Parents need the strength of spirit to force a child to engage in an activity that is painful for him. A child is a favorite child! - can cry and resist, so Western parents who do not have the strength to withstand the tears and pleas of their child, as a rule, give up immediately. Chinese parents do not give up. And the Chinese strategy works: the tears of a child offended by extra work are then returned to them with his tears of gratitude.

It seems that in the case of Western education, a happy but uncompetitive child is raised. And, allegedly, in the case of Eastern upbringing - strong, successful, but unhappy. As always, in theory, the best option is somewhere in the middle, as a mix between Western and Eastern education. After all, the psychological development of a child depends on a large number of factors [7]. Among them are the behavioral reactions of the surrounding people and environmental factors.

Atthesametime,
oneshouldalwaysrememberthenegativeimpactofstress,whatresearchersrepeatedlynotei
nscientificpublications [1 - 9,16,17], whichleadsto a
decreasefunctionallyxopportunitycardiorespiratorysystem [10-14]
andpossibleproblemsofthedigestivesystemandmusculoskeletalsystem.

And also, one should not forget about age characteristics and educational tasks that are characteristic for each age group period, certainly. There are some tasks for an infant, others for a 2-3-year-old child, and starting from 4 years old, the tasks change again. And in accordance with these tasks, it is necessary to select the types of activities and classes, their forms. At the same time, maintaining psychological balance, using methods of increasing stress resistance, preventing high levels of anxiety, and the use of health-preserving technologies and the development of emotional intelligence contribute to this [1-6, 16, 17].

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